

Indirect mineral carbonation of recycled concrete aggregate: Enhancing calcium extraction using a packed bed reactor

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ABSTRACT

Mineral carbonation of industrial residues is gaining increasing interest, with the first pilot and industrial-scale applications being implemented. The process offers a low-risk, easily available solution for permanent carbon dioxide storage while concurrently valorising industrial wastes. This work investigates the indirect mineral carbonation of recycled concrete aggregate (RCA), in which calcium is first leached from the RCA into an aqueous ammonium nitrate (AN) solution, followed by carbonation to yield high-purity precipitated calcium carbonate. The study focuses on the first step, calcium dissolution, which traditionally takes place in a stirred batch reactor (SBR). However, SBRs often encounter solubility constraints, leading to low calcium extraction yields. In this investigation, we explore the application of a packed bed reactor (PBR) and demonstrate its superior performance, resulting in a calcium extraction enhancement of 27% to 55% relative to SBRs, across AN concentrations ranging from 0.25 to 2.0 mol/kg, at 25 °C and atmospheric pressure. The PBR's superior performance can be attributed to the more compact design, enabling longer dissolution times, and to the continuous supply of fresh solvent, effectively reducing solubility limitations. The impact of key operating parameters (AN concentration, liquid flow rate and extraction time) are systemically assessed experimentally, accurately modelled using a shrinking-core model, and illustrated in process performance maps. Furthermore, this research highlights the significance of ammonium nitrate recovery from the wet solids after filtration to ensure the process's environmental viability. The packed bed reactor (PBR) functions as an integrated filter, facilitating the straightforward recovery of 80% of the trapped ammonium nitrate solution through simple water flushing. In conclusion, the utilisation of PBRs in indirect mineral carbonation presents an innovative and efficient approach for enhancing calcium extraction while addressing environmental concerns through ammonium nitrate recovery. The applicability of PBRs extends beyond recycled concrete aggregates, and could also be successfully applied for other coarse industrial residues such as steel slags.

1. Introduction

To limit warming to below 2 °C, substantial emission reductions are required over the next decades. Carbon capture, utilisation, and storage (CCUS) will be a key instrument for mitigating point-source emissions (IPCC, 2021). For small-scale industrial CCUS, a mitigation solution is offered by ex-situ mineral carbonation: an accelerated form of natural rock weathering. Many industrial residues have been studied for mineralisation (Sanna et al., 2014): steel-making slags (Huijgen et al., 2005; Eloneva et al., 2012), fuel combustion ashes (Rendek et al., 2006; He et al., 2013), alkaline paper mill wastes (Pérez-López et al., 2008; Kim and Kim, 2018), cement kiln dusts (Huntzinger et al., 2009; Kim et al., 2017), and recycled concrete aggregates (RCA) (Ben Ghacham et al., 2017; Tiefenthaler et al., 2021; Meijssen et al., 2023b). Mineralisation of these industrial residues has the potential to permanently

store up to 360 Mt of CO₂ per annum in the form of carbonated minerals (Pan et al., 2020), without the risks of leakage and induced seismicity that are in principle associated with CO₂ geological storage (Bui et al., 2018). The process also creates value through valorisation and utilisation of the resulting products (Bobicki et al., 2012).

Among industrial sectors, the cement and concrete industries may conveniently deploy such technologies (Skocek et al., 2020; Winnefeld et al., 2022), because of the opportunity, i.e. the abundance of RCA (ca. 34 Gt of concrete produced in 2020 (GCCS, 2021)), and because of the need, i.e. the large emissions of cement manufacturing (ca. 7% of worldwide CO₂ emissions (IEA, 2018)). However, due to the low theoretical storage potential of RCA, ca. 45 kg of CO₂ per ton RCA (Habert et al., 2020), large volumes of materials must be handled, making the full-scale deployment challenging. Nevertheless,

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Nomenclature

Latin symbols

c	Calcium liquid concentration [mol/m ³]
c^*	c of saturated solvent [mol/m ³]
c_{AN}	Ammonium nitrate concentration [mol/m ³]
c_i	c in the pores of particle size bin i [mol/m ³]
D	Calcium molecular diffusivity [m ² /s]
d	Diameter of the reactor [m]
D_e	Effective calcium diffusivity [m ² /s]
k_b	Bed permeability [m ²]
k_d	Calcium dissolution rate constant [1/s]
k_f	Film mass transfer coefficient [m/s]
l	Length of the reactor [m]
m	Mass [kg]
n	Calcium solid concentration [mol/kg]
p	Pressure [Pa]
Q	Liquid flow rate [m ³ /s]
\bar{q}	Average particle calcium conc. [mol/m ³]
R	Particle radius [m]
r	Particle radial coordinate [m]
T	Temperature [K]
t	Time [s]
u	Liquid interstitial velocity [m/s]
V	Volume of reactor [m ³]
W	Specific solvent pumping power [W/kg]
z	Packed bed coordinate [m]

Greek symbols

γ	Solvent calcium saturation [-]
ϵ	Void fraction [-]
η	Solids' calcium extraction yield [-]
Θ	Dimensionless particle radius [-]
κ_{ov}	Overall mass transfer coefficient [-]
μ	Liquid dynamic viscosity [Pa s]
ν	Phase ratio [-]
ξ	Dimensionless packed bed coordinate [-]
ρ	Density [kg/m ³]
σ	Phase calcium capacity ratio [-]
τ_e	Particle pores tortuosity [-]
ϕ_i	Volumetric fraction of size bin i [-]
χ	Dimensionless particle radial coordinate [-]
Ψ	Solvent consumption [-]
ω_i	Weight fraction of size bin i [-]

Subscripts

b	Bulk liquid
c	Shrinking core
i	Particle size bin
l	Liquid
o	Outlet of the reactor
p	Produced liquid
r	Recovered liquid at the washing step
s	Solid

Fig. 1. Process flow diagram of the indirect mineral carbonation of recycled concrete aggregate (RCA). Fresh solvent, i.e. aqueous ammonium nitrate, makes up for the liquid losses in the filtered materials. The feedstocks, products, and process steps are indicated in orange, green, and grey, respectively. The section of the process investigated in this study is identified by the dashed box.

Rosa et al. (2022) indicated that the storage of biogenic CO₂ in RCA is a promising and efficient carbon dioxide removal opportunity for small emitters, such as biogas facilities, given the short CO₂ transport distances to concrete recyclers.

Indirect aqueous mineral carbonation (IMC) offers faster reaction rates compared to direct carbonation processes (Sipilä et al., 2008). IMC, schematised in Fig. 1, is a process in which the calcium is leached out from the waste material in a first step, i.e. the dissolution, while CO₂ absorption and precipitation to calcium carbonate (CaCO₃) occur in a second step, i.e. the carbonation. The mother liquor from the carbonation step is subsequently recycled to the first step of the process (Kodama et al., 2008). The process produces: (1) decalcified RCA that can be used as aggregate for concrete, improving the concrete strength compared to the use of fresh RCA due to the removal of the attached cement mortar (Tam et al., 2007, 2021), and (2) pure precipitated calcium carbonate that can be utilised as raw material for clinker production or in higher-value applications (Mattila and Zevenhoven, 2014; Jimoh et al., 2018). Ammonium salt solutions (NH₄NO₃, NH₄Cl, or CH₃COONH₄ (Jo et al., 2014)) are used as solvent to enhance the leaching of calcium and the absorption of CO₂ because of their good performance as a pH buffer and their superior recyclability as compared to strong acidic solutions such as HCl (Liu et al., 2021). In addition, ammonium salts, unlike stronger acids (Vanderzee and Zeman, 2018), do not dissolve the limestone in the RCA, which already binds CO₂.

Our recent pilot scale study sheds light on the environmental and technical challenges associated with the dissolution step of IMC (Meijssen et al., 2023b). First, the dissolution step is kinetically limited by calcium diffusion out of the particles' pores; RCA particles larger than 0.5 mm in diameter require over an hour of leaching time. Crushing the RCA for faster diffusion is not an option, since the resulting material cannot be used as aggregate in concrete anymore. Second, the solubility of the calcium-bearing phases in the solvent limits the dissolution. Calcium hydroxide (C-H) and calcium silicate hydrate (C-S-H) are the primary mineral phases leached out from RCA; the latter undergoes incongruent dissolution causing its solubility to decrease significantly as the mineral phase decalcifies (Berner, 1992; Gérard et al., 2002). Because of kinetic and equilibrium limitations, leaching calcium from RCA in stirred batch reactors using an aqueous ammonium salt solution rarely exceeds 50% yield at relevant operating conditions (Meijssen and Mazzotti, 2022). Finally, part of the solvent is lost in the filtered solids, resulting in large GHG emissions related to ammonium nitrate synthesis; thus, a suitable solvent recovery approach must be implemented.

A flow-through packed bed reactor, which is widely used for the extraction of vegetable matrices from plant materials (De Melo et al.,

2014), may address the aforementioned challenges. The packed bed offers longer leaching times than a stirred reactor because of its lower volume at a given solid throughput, which may tackle the kinetic limitations. Additionally, the continuous supply of fresh solvent in a packed bed reactor allows the exhaustive extraction of the feedstock, thereby reducing the influence of equilibrium limitations on the dissolution rate (Uhlenbrock et al., 2020). The main disadvantage of such a reactor is the requirement for a pressurised vessel due to the pressure drop along the bed.

This work specifically addresses the challenges of the dissolution step of indirect mineral carbonation, i.e., the low calcium extraction yield and the solvent losses, with a novel packed bed reactor. The calcium leaching from RCA using an ammonium nitrate aqueous solution is examined experimentally and modelled, and the performance is compared to that of stirred batch reactors. The following is the structure of the paper. The experimental study's methodologies are outlined in Section 2. Section 3 describes the calcium leaching process using a first-principles model. Section 4 provides and discusses the key findings of this study, including the model performance, the packed bed reactor leaching kinetics and solvent recovery, as well as some scale-up considerations. Finally, Section 5 draws conclusions.

2. Methods

2.1. Materials

A concrete recycler in Switzerland supplied the recycled concrete aggregate used as feedstock for mineral carbonation. The RCA was dried in an oven at 105 °C for 24 h before being divided into five size fractions, given by the sieve mesh size: (1) less than 0.25 mm, (2) 0.25–0.50 mm, (3) 0.50–1.0 mm, (4) 1.0–2.0 mm, and (5) 2.0–4.0 mm. Each size fraction was divided into sub-samples using a sample splitter and stored in capped containers. The original particle size distribution was reconstructed for each experiment. The aqueous ammonium nitrate solution employed as a solvent was prepared using ultra-pure water (resistivity of 18.2 MΩ cm at 25 °C) and ammonium nitrate at ≥ 99% purity (Sigma-Aldrich).

2.2. Experimental setup and procedure

The packed bed extraction process is illustrated in Fig. 2 as a series of five steps: (1) filling the reactor with fines, (2) filling the reactor with solvent, which causes a liquid front to move towards the outlet, (3) pumping solvent through the reactor to leach calcium from the fines, (4) pumping water through the reactor to displace the trapped solvent out and to recover it, and (5) removing the wet fines from the reactor. This work focuses on steps (2–4); steps (1) and (5) are less relevant here because their operation depends on the specific scale of application.

The experimental setup consists of a 393 mL pressure filter (BHS Sonthofen Taschenmessgerät PLF) with dimensions of 20 cm in length and 5 cm in diameter. A filter paper (Macherey-Nagel MN-615) is inserted at the reactor's outlet to retain the material; this is not strictly necessary because less than 0.1 wt.% of the particles are washed out. The reactor is filled with 570 g of well-mixed RCA and gently tapped to distribute the solids properly. The aqueous ammonium nitrate solution of given concentration c_{AN} is then pumped through the packed bed using a progressive cavity pump (Rototec RCA 35) for flow rates larger than 12 g/min, and an HPLC pump (Jasco PU 987) for smaller flow rates. The solvent temperature is maintained at 25 ± 1 °C using an electrical heater (HORST HTMC1). The eluate is collected in a stirred buffer tank, and its weight is monitored with a scale (Mettler-Toledo XP64001L). Additionally, a pressure sensor (Keller PR-35X) is used to monitor the pressure drop through the packed bed. The first liquid outlet defines the transition from the liquid filling to the calcium leaching phases. Then, liquid samples of 0.5 mL are taken at various

points in time, both at the reactor's outlet and in the stirred buffer tank. The extraction yield is calculated as follows:

$$\eta(t) = \frac{m_p(t) c_p(t)}{m_s \sum_{i=1}^5 \omega_i n_{0,i}} \quad (1)$$

where m_p and c_p stand for the weight and calcium concentration of the liquid product in the buffer, respectively. The variable m_s refers to the initial solids' mass; ω_i and $n_{0,i}$ are the weight fraction and initial calcium concentration of the particles in size bin i , respectively. The latter quantity is obtained via batch leaching in a 4 mol/kg ammonium nitrate solution for 24 h, and with a solid loading of 5% (Meijssen and Mazzotti, 2022). In this study, the ammonium nitrate concentration and solvent flow rate were varied from 0.25 to 2.0 mol/kg and from 5 to 30 g/min, respectively.

After the calcium leaching phase, the reactor is filled with aqueous ammonium nitrate solution; two solvent recovery methodologies are investigated: (1) injecting 2.5 bar pressurised air into the reactor for 60 s, thereby decreasing its liquid content, and (2) pumping water through the reactor, thereby displacing the ammonium nitrate solution. To avoid evaporation of ammonia prior to measurement, the outflow is collected and quenched at 5 °C. The weight of the recovered solvent, m_r , and its ammonia concentration, $c_{AN,r}$, are measured to estimate the ammonium nitrate recovery:

$$\varphi_{AN} = \frac{m_r c_{AN,r}}{\epsilon V \rho_1 c_{AN}} \quad (2)$$

where ϵ is the packed bed porosity and ρ_1 is the solvent density. The solvent remains unchanged for the pressurised air method, hence $c_{AN,r} = c_{AN}$ in that case.

2.3. Analytical methods

The total concentrations of Li, Na, NH₄, K, Mg and Ca in the liquid samples were measured using ion chromatography (IC, Dionex ICS-2000), as described by Thomas et al. (2002). The samples were filtered using 0.45 μm hydrophilic filters to eliminate particles, and then diluted to be within the technique measurement range.

The chemical composition of the RCA was measured by X-ray fluorescence (XRF, PANalytical Axios Advanced). The weight loss from 500 °C to 900 °C determined by thermogravimetric analysis (TGA, Mettler Toledo TGA/DSC 3+ STARE System) gives the amount of carbonated calcium, i.e. CaCO₃. Dry vibratory sieving (Retsch AS 200) was used to determine the particle size distribution. The solids' porosity was quantified with a low-temperature (77 K) N₂ adsorption BET apparatus (Microtrac Belsorp Max).

3. Packed bed extractor model

The model describes the irreversible dissolution of calcium from a porous solid into an aqueous ammonium nitrate solution, followed by calcium ions diffusion out of the pores of the solid into the bulk of the fluid phase. Meijssen et al. (2023a) previously showed that the calcium leaching from recycled concrete aggregate in a stirred batch reactor can be described using a shrinking-core model, i.e. by assuming that a sharp boundary exists between a leached outer core and an unleached inner core of the particles. Shrinking-core models have also been used to describe calcium dissolution from other industrial mineral wastes (Seo et al., 2018; Hosseini et al., 2014; Baldyga et al., 2011; Dri et al., 2013). The sharp boundary may exist when calcium mass transfer out of the particle is much slower than the rate of solid dissolution, or the calcium available in the solids is much higher than the solvent calcium capacity in the pores. In this work, we use a single shrinking core, thereby lumping C-H and C-S-H into a single dissolving phase undergoing incongruent dissolution. The reader is referred to our previous work for calcium leaching models that account for both phases separately (Meijssen et al., 2023a); however, these models are computationally more expensive and less suitable for process optimisation.

Fig. 2. Schematic of the successive steps of a packed bed dissolution cycle: (1) reactor filling with solids, (2) reactor filling with solvent, (3) pumping fresh solvent to leach calcium, (4) pumping water for solvent recovery, and (5) reactor emptying. The operating parameters and measured quantities are indicated by boxes and circles, respectively.

3.1. Shrinking-core model

For a packed bed extractor and monodisperse particles, Goto et al. (1996) derived the shrinking-core model equations. They assumed an isothermal process with axial solvent flow across a packed bed of length l , with an interstitial velocity u . In this work, we assume no axial dispersion and describe the particle size distribution using five size bins $i = 1, \dots, 5$ with mean particle size R_i , and their associated volumetric fraction ϕ_i . The bulk fluid-phase material balance characterises the calcium concentration c_b as a function of time t and bed position z ; it is coupled with Eq. (6) that describes the rate of depletion of the average solid phase calcium concentration \bar{q}_i :

$$\frac{\partial c_b}{\partial t} + u \frac{\partial c_b}{\partial z} = -\frac{1 - \epsilon_b}{\epsilon_b} \sum_{i=1}^5 \phi_i (1 - \epsilon_{s,i}) \frac{\partial \bar{q}_i}{\partial t} \quad (3)$$

The variables ϵ_b and $\epsilon_{s,i}$ refer to the porosity of the bed and of the solid particles, respectively. The total void fraction ϵ is given by:

$$\epsilon = \epsilon_b + (1 - \epsilon_b) \sum_{i=1}^5 \phi_i \epsilon_{s,i} \quad (4)$$

Under the shrinking-core assumption, the average value of the solid-phase calcium concentration and the inner core radius, $r_{c,i}$, are coupled through mass balance considerations, hence:

$$\bar{q}_i = \bar{q}_{0,i} \left(\frac{r_{c,i}}{R_i} \right)^3 \quad (5)$$

Calcium dissolution is limited by three mass-transfer resistances in series: (i) calcium dissolution from the solid phase into the liquid phase, with a dissolution reaction rate constant k_d , (ii) calcium diffusion through the pores from the inner core to the particle's surface, with an effective diffusivity D_e , and (iii) calcium diffusion through an external film surrounding the particle, with a film mass transfer coefficient $k_{f,i}$. The average calcium content of a particle varies according to:

$$\frac{\partial \bar{q}_i}{\partial t} = \frac{\epsilon_{s,i}}{(1 - \epsilon_{s,i})} \frac{1}{\frac{R_i}{3k_{f,i}} + \frac{R_i^3}{3D_e} \left(\frac{1}{r_{c,i}} - \frac{1}{R_i} \right) + \frac{\epsilon_{s,i} \epsilon_i^*}{k_d(1 - \epsilon_{s,i}) \bar{q}_{0,i}}} (c_b - c_i^*) \quad (6)$$

whose derivation is given in the Supplementary Information. The variable c_i^* is the concentration of calcium at equilibrium with the solid phase of particle size bin i , which differs from the solubility of $\text{Ca}(\text{OH})_2$ in aqueous ammonium nitrate, c^* , as detailed later in this Section. The effective diffusivity D_e is given by:

$$D_e = \frac{D}{\tau_e} \quad (7)$$

where τ_e is the solids' pores tortuosity and D is the calcium molecular diffusivity.

3.2. Dimensionless system of equations

Dimensionless dependent variables ($\gamma_b = \frac{c_b}{c^*}$ and $\chi_i = \frac{r_i}{R_i}$), and independent variables ($\xi = \frac{z}{L}$ and $\tau = \frac{t}{(R^2/D)}$), are defined. The volume-averaged particle diameter \bar{R} is chosen as the characteristic particle length. In addition, the following dimensionless parameters are introduced, namely $\Theta_i = \frac{R_i}{\bar{R}}$, $\nu = \frac{\epsilon}{(1 - \epsilon)}$, $\sigma_i = \frac{\bar{q}_{0,i}}{\nu_{s,i} c^*}$, $\text{Pe} = \frac{u \bar{R}^2}{D l}$, $\text{Sh}_i = \frac{2k_{f,i} R_i}{D}$, $\text{Da}_i = \frac{\sigma_i k_d R_i^2}{D}$, in order to construct the dimensionless equations for the packed bed reactor:

$$\frac{\partial \gamma_b}{\partial \tau} + \text{Pe} \frac{\partial \gamma_b}{\partial \xi} = -\frac{3}{\nu_b} \sum_{j=1}^5 \phi_j \epsilon_{s,j} \kappa_{\text{ov},j} (\gamma_b - \gamma_j^*) \quad (8)$$

$$\frac{\partial \chi_{c,i}}{\partial \tau} = \frac{1}{\sigma_i \chi_{c,i}^2} \kappa_{\text{ov},i} (\gamma_b - \gamma_i^*) \quad (9)$$

$$\kappa_{\text{ov},i} = \frac{1}{\Theta_i^2 \left(\frac{2}{\text{Sh}_i} + \tau_e \left(\frac{1}{\chi_{c,i}} - 1 \right) + \frac{3\gamma_i^*}{\text{Da}_i} \right)} \quad (10)$$

where $\kappa_{\text{ov},i}$ is the overall mass transfer coefficient of particle i . The reactor contains initially no solvent, and the process starts with a liquid front travelling through the reactor until the liquid reaches the reactor's outlet at $\tau_r = \text{Pe}^{-1}$, i.e. the dimensionless liquid residence time. We define two extraction performance indicators:

- The calcium extraction yield from the solids η , i.e. the fraction of the calcium available in the solids that has been recovered in the liquid product:

$$\frac{d\eta}{d\tau} = \nu_b \text{Pe} \frac{\gamma_b(\xi = 1)}{\sum_{j=1}^5 \phi_j \epsilon_{s,j} \sigma_j} \quad (11)$$

where $\gamma_b(\xi = 1)$ is the calcium saturation in the liquid outflow.

- The liquid product calcium saturation γ_p , i.e. the average calcium saturation of the reactor liquid outflow since the beginning of the extraction:

$$\frac{d\gamma_p}{d\tau} = \frac{1}{(\tau - \tau_r)} (\gamma_b(\xi = 1) - \gamma_p) \quad (12)$$

The initial conditions are:

$$\gamma_b = 0 \quad \text{at} \quad \tau = 0 \quad (13)$$

$$\chi_{c,i} = 1 - \delta \quad \text{at} \quad \tau = 0 \quad (14)$$

$$\eta = 0 \quad \text{at} \quad \tau = \tau_r \quad (15)$$

$$\gamma_p = \gamma_b(\xi = 1) \quad \text{at} \quad \tau = \tau_r \quad (16)$$

where $\delta = 10^{-4}$ is chosen for numerical reasons. The boundary conditions are:

$$\gamma_b = 0 \quad \text{at} \quad \xi = 0 \quad (17)$$

$$\frac{\partial \gamma_b}{\partial \xi} = 0 \quad \text{at} \quad \xi = 1 \quad (18)$$

The set of partial differential equations (Eqs. (8), (9), (11) and (12)), coupled with boundary and initial conditions (Eqs. (13)–(18)), is solved numerically by the finite difference method using the upwind difference scheme. The dimensionless reactor coordinate ξ is divided into 75 bins. For $\tau < \tau_r$, a moving liquid boundary exists; the problem is solved using the Landau transformation $\tilde{\xi} = \frac{\xi}{\xi_b(t)}$ suggested by Myers et al. (2022), where ξ_b is the position of the moving boundary. The modified equations are available in the Supplementary Information (Equations (S4) to (S10)).

3.3. Model correlations and constants

The volumetric fraction of bin size i is computed from the weight fraction ω_i , the true density $\rho_{s,i}$, and the porosity $\epsilon_{s,i}$ of the particles of bin size i :

$$\phi_i = \frac{\omega_i / (\rho_{s,i}(1 - \epsilon_{s,i}))}{\sum_{j=1}^5 \omega_j / (\rho_{s,j}(1 - \epsilon_{s,j}))} \quad (19)$$

The density ρ_l and the dynamic viscosity μ_l of the ammonium nitrate aqueous solution were taken from Friend et al. (2007) and Campbell et al. (1953), respectively. Both quantities are obtained as function of temperature and ammonium nitrate concentration by piecewise interpolation. The calcium molecular diffusivity in aqueous ammonium nitrate solutions is correlated to the diffusivity of calcium in water at 25 °C ($D_w = 1.59 \cdot 10^{-9} \text{ m}^2 \text{ s}^{-1}$) (Atkins and de Paula, 2006) using Stokes–Einstein equations:

$$D = D_w \frac{(T/\mu)}{(T_w/\mu_w)} \quad (20)$$

The Sherwood number correlation for packed beds with spherical particles from Wakao and Kagei (1982) is used, where the Reynolds and Schmidt numbers are given by $Re = \frac{2\epsilon_b \rho_l u R_i}{\mu_l}$ and $Sc = \frac{\mu_l}{\rho_l D}$, respectively.

$$Sh = 2.0 + 1.1 Sc^{1/3} Re^{0.6} \quad (21)$$

The linear approximation proposed in our earlier work (Meijssen and Mazzotti, 2022) is used to compute the solubility of calcium in the aqueous ammonium nitrate solution at 25 °C, which is fitted on the predicted values using the thermodynamic package EQ3/6.

$$c^* = 0.497 c_{AN} + 0.0129 [\text{mol L}^{-1}] \quad (22)$$

As previously stated, calcium hydroxide (C-H) and calcium silica hydrate (C-S-H) phases are primarily leached from RCA. The latter undergoes incongruent dissolution, i.e. the solid is gradually depleted of calcium, transforming into another mineral phase with decreasing solubility (Bernier, 1992; Gérard et al., 2002). To account for incongruent dissolution, the following empirical formula for the liquid concentration at equilibrium with the solid phase of particle i , γ_i^* , is utilised:

$$\gamma_i^* = \alpha + (1 - \alpha) \chi_{c,i}^3 \quad (23)$$

The empirical formula translates the reduction in solid phase solubility with leaching extent from $\gamma_i^* = 1$ (C-H) to $\gamma_i^* = \alpha$ (decalcified C-S-H). The solubility of the fully decalcified C-S-H in water and in ammonium nitrate has been proposed to be 10% of the solubility of C-H in the

solution (Nakarai et al., 2006; Wan et al., 2013); therefore, $\alpha = 0.1$ was chosen. This calculation, however, may underestimate the effective diffusion coefficient because of the artificially low solubility of the calcium phases located close to the particles' centre.

Finally, the model equations contain two parameters that must be estimated by fitting relevant experimental data: the pores tortuosity τ_e , and the dissolution reaction rate constant k_d .

4. Results and discussion

4.1. Material characterisation

The chemical composition of the RCA is reported in Table 1; the main components are SiO_2 (43.3 wt.%) and CaO (27.8 wt.%), whereby CaO exists in the form of calcium hydroxide ($\text{Ca}(\text{OH})_2$), calcium silicate hydrate ($x\text{CaO} \cdot \text{SiO}_2 \cdot y\text{H}_2\text{O}$) and calcium carbonate (CaCO_3). The maximal extractable calcium from the RCA ($n_{0,i}$ in Table 2) measured experimentally results in a CO_2 sequestration capacity of 39.0 kg CO_2 per ton RCA by indirect mineral carbonation. The maximum theoretical amount of CO_2 stored in the recycled concrete aggregate is calculated using the formula suggested by Steinosaur (1959):

$$\left[\omega_{\text{CO}_2}^{\text{stored}} \right]_{\text{Steinosaur}} = 0.785 (\omega_{\text{CaO}} - 0.56 \omega_{\text{CaCO}_3} - 0.7 \omega_{\text{SiO}_3}) \quad (24)$$

where ω_j is the mass fraction of component j in RCA. The formula is based on the assumption that all the calcium contained in the material may react with CO_2 to form CaCO_3 , besides the calcium already bound in CaCO_3 ($\omega_{\text{CaCO}_3} = 38.3$ wt.% as measured by TGA) and in CaSO_4 (not measured, but typically small for concrete). Thus, the theoretical CO_2 sequestration capacity of the RCA is 49.8 kg of CO_2 per ton, which is higher than measured experimentally. The limestone (CaCO_3) is not leached from the RCA using aqueous ammonium nitrate due to the alkaline conditions. The decalcification of the C-S-H phase results in a meta-stable phase of C-S-H in the solids, tobermorite, that still contains calcium (calcium to silica ratio of 0.833) (Trapote-Barreira et al., 2014; Castellote et al., 2009). The contribution of this trapped calcium to the CO_2 storage potential of the RCA must be deducted from Eq. (24), thereby decreasing the CO_2 sequestration capacity.

The leached RCA is expected to perform better as aggregate for concrete than fresh RCA, i.e., to exhibit lower water absorption and higher compressive strength, as observed in previous studies (Meijssen et al., 2023b; Tam et al., 2021). Ammonium nitrate has a deleterious effect on concrete since it dissolves the hydrated cement, thereby decreasing the compressive strength (Schneider and Chen, 2005; Bibi et al., 2020). Some ammonium nitrate remains in the pores of the leached RCA; however, the amount is small and the conditions are different as compared to the previously cited studies, and the solution in the pores will be saturated with calcium. Thus, we expect hardly any impact of the remaining ammonium nitrate, but further investigation is needed.

The chemical and physical properties of each size fraction of the material are reported in Table 2. The particle size distribution reported earlier (Meijssen and Mazzotti, 2022) was used, which represents a typical PSD for these materials. The cement paste is more easily crushed than the coarse material of the RCA; therefore the finer fractions are richer in hydrated cement paste (Florea and Brouwers, 2013). This is confirmed by the larger available calcium concentration $n_{0,i}$ and void fraction $\epsilon_{s,i}$, and the lower true density $\rho_{s,i}$ of the finer fractions.

Table 1

Chemical composition (components over 0.1 wt.%), measured with XRF, of the recycled concrete aggregate with a reconstructed particle size distribution. LOI stands for loss on ignition at 1050 °C.

SiO2	CaO	Al2O3	Fe2O3	K2O	MgO	Na2O	LOI
43.3	27.8	3.85	1.43	0.85	0.84	0.62	20.0 [wt.%]

Table 2

Properties of the recycled concrete aggregate size bins, in terms of: (i) weight fraction ω_i , (ii) particle true density $\rho_{p,i}$, (iii) particle void fraction $\epsilon_{p,i}$ from Florea and Brouwers (2013), and (iv) solid-phase initial available calcium concentration $n_{0,i}$ and $\bar{q}_{0,i}$. The properties of the mixed material are weighted averages.

Size [μm]	ω_i [wt.%]	$\rho_{p,i}$ [kg/L]	$\epsilon_{p,i}$ [%]	$n_{0,i}$ [mol/kg]	$\bar{q}_{0,i}$ [mol/L]
0–250	17	2.35	14.7	1.23	2.82
250–500	12	2.40	8.91	0.90	2.12
500–1000	16	2.45	7.62	0.88	2.10
1000–2000	24	2.47	6.33	0.84	2.02
2000–4000	31	2.48	4.31	0.73	1.76
Mixed	100	2.44	7.71	0.89	2.11

Table 3

Results of the parameter estimation of the model based on the experimental measurements, including the 95% confidence interval of the estimates. The mean relative error and coefficient of determination for the estimation of the extraction yield is 5.3% and 0.994, respectively.

Parameter	Estimate	[95% CI]
τ_e [-]	1.536	[1.53, 1.54]
k_d [s^{-1}]	6.29×10^{-4}	$[6.24, 6.33] \times 10^{-4}$

4.2. Model performance

The model described in Section 3 was fitted to experimental data (8 operating conditions and 91 experimental points). The sum of the squared normalised residuals of the extraction yield was minimised for the parameter estimation using MATLAB's integrated algorithm *lsqnonlin*. The estimated values and the 95% confidence intervals of the fitted parameters, i.e. τ_e and k_d , are reported in Table 3. In the range of operating conditions investigated, the model fit of the extraction yield is satisfactory, with a mean relative error (MRE) of 5.3% and a coefficient of determination (R^2) of 0.994; parity plots are available in the Supplementary Information (Figure S1). For accurate modelling of other recycled concrete aggregates, e.g., pre-treated or from another provenance, the RCA-specific properties listed in Table 2 must be remeasured and the model parameters may be estimated to relevant experiments following the developed approach.

4.3. Technical analysis of the calcium leaching step

Calcium leaching phases. The experiment performed at $Q = 15$ g/min and $c_{\text{AN}} = 0.25$ mol/kg is used to discuss the leaching step. The elution profiles are depicted in Fig. 3, in terms of the solvent saturation at the reactor outlet γ_o (left panel), as well as the total extraction yield η and the calcium saturation of the liquid product γ_p (right panel).

Fig. 3. Time profile of measured quantities during a calcium leaching experiment operated with $c_{\text{AN}} = 0.25$ mol/kg, $Q = 15$ g/min, $T = 25$ °C. The saturated solvent ($\gamma = 1$) concentration is 0.137 mol/kg. **Left:** outlet solvent saturation with respect to calcium (black), potassium (green) and sodium (red). **Right:** liquid product solvent saturation (squares) and the extraction yield (circles). SL: solubility-limited regime; MIX: mixed regime; DL: diffusion-limited regime.

The dissolution kinetics are influenced by different mechanisms, which suggests dividing the elution profile into three regions:

- **Solubility-limited regime (SL):** at the start of the extraction process, the calcium is easily accessible and the kinetics are limited by the solubility of the C-H and C-S-H phases. The transport of calcium in the bulk liquid is slower than the calcium diffusion out of the particles and the liquid is close to saturation. Moreover, the alkalis Na and K coming from the cement paste are quickly leached out due to their weak binding to the matrix. The dissolution of these impurities releases hydroxide ions, thereby significantly increasing the solution pH and reducing the solubility of the calcium-bearing phases (Gérard et al., 2002). As a consequence, there exists a maximum in the outlet solvent saturation profile when the alkali content in the solution decrease. It should be noted that alkalis are known to increase the expansion and cracking of concrete via alkali-aggregate reactions (Fournier and Bérubé, 2000; Leemann and Lothenbach, 2008); hence, alkali leaching may result in an improved aggregate.
- **Mixed regime (MIX):** the leaching kinetics are limited by calcium solubility and diffusion. The particles' external layer has been substantially leached out and contains poorly soluble decalcified C-S-H. The particles' inner core contains more soluble phases, but their dissolution is limited by pore diffusion.
- **Diffusion-limited regime (DL):** the majority of the remaining calcium is located in the particles' inner core, and pore diffusion controls the leaching kinetics. The eluate contains a small amount of calcium, which leads to significant product dilution as seen by the decreased liquid product saturation γ_p . To leach the remaining hard-to-access calcium, the solvent consumption and reaction time increase significantly.

The solubility constraints can be reduced either by increasing the calcium uptake capacity of the liquid (higher ammonium nitrate concentration) or by accelerating the transport of calcium out of the reactor (higher liquid flow rate). Grinding the particles is particularly effective to overcome diffusion constraints, but it would make it impossible to use RCA as an aggregate for concrete. The model is used hereafter to understand the effect of various operating parameters on the calcium leaching performance.

Effect of ammonium nitrate concentration. The presence of additional NO_3^- in solution enhances C-H and C-S-H solubility (Gérard et al., 2002). Fig. 4 illustrates the measured and predicted extraction yield as a function of time for AN concentrations ranging from 0.25 to 2.0 mol/kg. The higher calcium uptake capacity of the solvent at higher AN concentration accelerates the solubility-limited regime, as seen by the increasing slope with c_{AN} of the extraction yield profile

Fig. 4. Recycled concrete aggregate extraction yield as a function of the leaching time at $T = 25\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ and for (left) an ammonium nitrate concentration from 0.25 to 2.0 mol/kg with $Q = 15\text{ g/min}$, and (right) a liquid flow rate from 5 to 30 g/min with $c_{\text{AN}} = 0.5\text{ mol/kg}$. The lines and markers indicate the model outputs and experimental results, respectively.

Table 4

Damköhler number Da_i , i.e. the ratio of characteristic diffusion and dissolution times, for bin sizes $i = 1, 3, 5$ and for an ammonium nitrate concentration of $c_{\text{AN}} = 0.25, 1.0$ and 2.0 mol/kg .

c_{AN} [mol/kg]	0–0.25 mm	0.50–1.0 mm	2.0–4.0 mm
0.25	0.25	0.78	19
1.0	0.007	0.21	5.1
2.0	0.004	0.11	2.7

at short leaching durations. Additionally, a higher AN concentration also enhances pores diffusion due to an increased driving force between the nearly saturated solvent in the pores and the bulk fluid. However, at the early stages of the leaching, the solids' dissolution is too slow compared to the diffusion to saturate the solvent contained in the pores, thus controlling the dissolution rate. This effect is more significant for (i) fine particles because of their higher porosity and shorter diffusion lengths (Meijssen and Mazzotti, 2022), and (ii) higher ammonium nitrate concentration because of the larger calcium capacity of the solution. Indeed, as shown in Table 4, the Damköhler number of the particles, i.e. the ratio of characteristic diffusion and dissolution times, decreases with decreasing particle size and increasing AN concentration.

Effect of liquid flow rate. An increased liquid flow rate Q has two effects: (i) accelerating the film mass transfer as a result of the higher liquid velocities, and (ii) accelerating the transport of calcium out of the reactor, thereby preventing the saturation of the solution in the bed. Similarly to increasing the ammonium nitrate concentration, an increased flow rate accelerates the extraction process in the solubility-limited regime, i.e. at short times, as shown in Fig. 4. When the process

becomes diffusion-limited, however, the extraction yield curves rapidly converge since the flow rate does not affect intraparticle diffusion rates. It is important to note that larger flow rates provide a more dilute outlet liquid stream, as discussed further in this section. To avoid dilution of the produced liquid, a variable flow rate was investigated: a high flow rate when the process is solubility limited, which decreases as the process becomes diffusion limited. However, the performance of the process did not significantly improve compared to the same amount of solvent fed at a constant flow rate (see Figure S2).

Effect of other operating parameters. Dimensions and temperature of the reactor can be adjusted; however, their impact on process performance is small (see Figure S3). A reactor with a larger height-to-diameter ratio has a faster liquid interstitial velocity for a given volume and flow rate, which reduces the film mass transfer limitations. Increasing the temperature accelerates diffusion, albeit the benefit is minor (Meijssen and Mazzotti, 2022), and temperature is upper-bounded to avoid ammonia evaporation (Said et al., 2016).

Leaching performance analysis. The choice of ammonium nitrate concentration and liquid flow rate is a trade-off between a good utilisation of the solids (high extraction yield) and of the solvent (produced liquid highly saturated with calcium). A saturated solvent is desired because it has: (i) a higher pH, which favours the precipitation of CaCO_3 in the subsequent steps of the process (Eloneva et al., 2008), and (ii) a lesser amount of solvent pumped through the mineral carbonation plant. In Fig. 5, the extraction yield (coloured areas) and produced liquid calcium saturation (dashed isolines) are shown as a function of the ammonium nitrate concentration and liquid flow rate for three leaching times: one, two and four hours. The following observations are made:

Fig. 5. Calcium extraction yield η (colour scale) and produced liquid calcium saturation γ_p (dashed contour lines) as a function of the ammonium nitrate concentration c_{AN} and the solvent flow rate Q for three leaching times: 1, 2 and 4 h.

Fig. 6. Global warming potential associated to the ammonium nitrate (AN) losses in the filtered solids as a function of the AN concentration in the solvent for three scenarios: no solvent recovery, blowing pressurised air (34.1% recovery), or washing with water (79.8% recovery). The impact of AN losses is larger than the maximum CO₂ storage of RCA in the red region, and lower than 25% of that value in the green region.

- Extraction yield and solvent saturation exhibit opposing trends;
- At any given dissolution time and liquid product saturation, operating at higher solvent concentration and lower flow rate results in a larger extraction yield;
- For a target average solvent saturation of 50%–70%, typical achievable extraction yields are 35%–50% (after 1 h), 50%–65% (after 2 h), and 60%–75% (after 4 h);
- The required leaching time nearly doubles to increase the extraction yield from 50% to 70%, and it quadruples in going from 70% to 90% (see Figure S4).

Other factors influencing the choice of optimal operating conditions include: loss of ammonium nitrate in the wet solids (increases with c_{AN}), pressure drop and pumping power (increases with Q), reactor volume (increases with t), and the performance of the subsequent process steps, particularly the carbonation step.

4.4. Ammonium nitrate aqueous solvent recovery step

A solvent regeneration phase is added at the end of the process, to recover the ammonium nitrate (AN) solution trapped in the reactor, i.e. 300 L of liquid per ton of solids, which is very important since an average of 1.58 kg of CO₂ equivalent are emitted per kg of AN produced in Europe (value from EcoInvent 3.9.1 database). To note that liquid losses also occur in the filtration step needed for batch-stirred reactors (Meijssen et al., 2023b; Said et al., 2016). The global

warming potential of the AN losses is shown as a function of the solvent AN concentration in Fig. 6, for three scenarios: (i) no solvent recovery, (ii) blowing pressurised air into the reactor to reduce liquid content, and (iii) pumping water through the reactor to displace the trapped solvent, where the volume of water pumped equals the volume of solvent trapped. The performance of both recovery methods was independent of AN concentration, with an average AN recovery rate of 34.1 (± 4.7)% and 79.8 (± 2.7)%, respectively. The results demonstrate that implementing the water wash allows recovering more ammonium nitrate than using pressurised air, although the recovery method is slower (ca. 10 min vs. 1 min) and increases the dissolution cycle time. The maximum storage potential of the solids is indicated as a reference in Fig. 6: operating conditions resulting in larger AN losses than CO₂ storage must be avoided (red region). The washing stage has a significant impact on the environmental performance of the process, and it should always be used.

The solvent losses impact should be significantly lower than the RCA CO₂ storage potential; a value of 25% is chosen for illustration. Under this constraint, the maximum AN concentration is 0.25, 0.39, and 1.2 mol/kg for the no recovery, pressurised air, and water wash cases, respectively. A solvent recovery step thus enables faster leaching and higher yields by allowing for higher AN concentrations. It is worth noting that other feedstock materials with greater carbon-storing potential may be leached at higher solvent concentrations, as losses account for a lesser part of the storage potential.

4.5. Pressure drop considerations for scale-up

The main energy consumption of the process comes from the pumping power needed to overcome the pressure drop through the packed bed. The pressure drop may be calculated using Darcy's Law, where k_b is the bed permeability in m²:

$$\Delta p = \frac{\mu_l \epsilon_b u}{k_b} - \rho_l g l \quad [\text{Pa}] \quad (25)$$

The pressure drop increases over time due to the accumulation of fines near the outlet of the reactor, i.e. the compacting of the bed, until steady state is reached. The steady-state pressure drop values measured during the experiments were used to estimate the bed permeability, namely $k_b = 3.9 (\pm 0.6)$ darcys. Additionally, the pumping power per mass of solids is given by:

$$W = \frac{v}{\tau_r} \frac{\rho_l}{\rho_s} \Delta p \quad [\text{W/kg}] \quad (26)$$

Using Eqs. (25) and (26), the pressure drop and the pump specific power are computed as a function of liquid residence time and reactor height. The results, as shown in Fig. 7, reveal that the pressure drop steeply increases with larger reactor height and smaller liquid residence

Fig. 7. Impact of liquid residence time and the packed bed reactor's length on (left) the pressure drop through the bed, and (right) the pumping power per mass of solids. The shaded areas indicate operating conditions for which the flow resistance is too low for the reactor to fill up with liquid. The bed permeance was estimated using experimental data at 3.9 (± 0.6) darcys.

times. In the darkened area, the bed's resistance is too low for the reactor to fill up with liquid. The system must be operated well away from this region to avoid bypassing part of the solids. The pressure drop will increase when the system is scaled up; the following guidelines are suggested:

- Scale-out the reactor, i.e. multiple columns operated in parallel: such a multi-column system also allows for continuous operation of the dissolution section (Uhlenbrock et al., 2020).
- Reduce the reactor's height-to-diameter ratio to increase the packed bed volume while limiting pressure drop and electricity consumption.
- Use a longer residence time in the reactor, which reduces pressure drop and pumping power at the expense of a less productive process.

Overall, these findings describe the trade-off between energy penalty and process productivity. This trade-off is determined by the relative costs of the two options; the high pressures and large flow rates necessitate more expensive reactors and pumps, whereas the low productivity option needs more space and more reactors.

4.6. Comparison with a stirred reactor

Stirred batch reactors have drawbacks for the leaching of calcium from recycled concrete aggregates due to their large volumes and sensitivity to solubility limitations. These challenges may be addressed with a packed bed reactor. For a given reactor volume and solid throughput, the packed bed reactor may run with longer dissolution times since ca. 60 vol.% of the reactor is filled with solids, compared to only 4–7 vol.% for usual stirred reactor operating conditions (10%–20% solid-to-liquid mass ratio).

Fig. 8 compares the calcium extraction yield from RCA using a stirred batch reactor (SBR) and a packed bed reactor (PBR); the potential amount of CO₂ stored by the leached calcium, assuming complete carbonation, is indicated for completeness. The experiments performed in the SBR followed the methods reported earlier (Meijssen and Mazzotti, 2022). The experiments SBR₁₈₀ and PBR₁₈₀ had an equal leaching time of 180 min, while SBR₃₀ and PBR₁₈₀ had comparable solid throughput and reactor volume but different leaching times of 30 and 180 min, respectively. The PBR outperformed the SBR in achieving high extraction yields, especially at high AN concentrations. This is because the dissolved calcium in the SBR inhibits further decalcification of poorly soluble C-S-H phases. Moreover, the longer dissolution time provided by the PBR allowed for significantly better utilisation of the storage potential of solids than in the SBR. Additionally, since the amount of solvent consumed in all experiments was the same, the PBR produced a solution with a higher calcium concentration. These findings confirm that the packed bed reactor can achieve higher calcium leaching productivity and that the continuous supply of fresh solvent in the reactor reduces the impact of solubility limitations on the dissolution rate. In addition, using a PBR eliminates the need for a filtration unit, thereby reducing the overall cost of the plant (or at least compensating for the complexity and higher cost of the PBR). A solvent recovery step is also easily implemented, recovering around 80% of the ammonium nitrate contained in the filtered solids.

It should be noted that the packed bed reactor is best suited for coarser particles, such as recycled concrete aggregate or steel slags, because of: (i) the high bed permeability, which reduces pressure drop and electricity consumption, whereas the stirring power required to suspend coarse particles in a reactor is high, and (ii) the slow dissolution kinetics, which requires relatively low solvent flow rates and benefit from the long dissolution time allowed by packed bed reactors. For finer particles, the pressure drop through the bed can be large and a stirred reactor is more suitable.

Fig. 8. Calcium extraction yield and corresponding CO₂ storage as a function of the ammonium nitrate concentration for a stirred batch reactor after 30 min (SBR₃₀) and 180 min (SBR₁₈₀), and for a packed bed reactor after 180 min at a flow rate of 15 g/min (PBR₁₈₀). The solid-to-liquid mass ratio and temperature are 20% and 25 °C for all experiments, respectively.

5. Conclusion

A packed bed reactor has been investigated for the extraction of calcium from recycled concrete aggregate (RCA) into an aqueous ammonium nitrate solution for indirect mineral carbonation, a process that combines carbon sequestration and waste upcycling. A concrete recycler provided the RCA fines (particles smaller than 4 mm), which had a maximum carbon storage potential of 39 kg of CO₂ per ton. Through an experimental campaign and the development of a model, the impact of major operational parameters on the calcium leaching kinetics was examined.

The extraction process is limited by the solubility of calcium-bearing solid phases in the liquid, and by calcium diffusion within the porous particles at the later stages. Calcium extraction can be improved by increasing the liquid flow rate, which prevents the bulk solution from becoming saturated, as well as the ammonium nitrate (AN) concentration, which decreases solubility limitations and promotes faster diffusion within the particle pores. However, it comes at the cost of a less saturated produced liquid, as well as larger pressure drop or ammonium nitrate loss, respectively.

Compared to a stirred batch reactor, the packed bed reactor demonstrated superior performance in terms of calcium extraction yield and saturation of the produced liquid, thanks to (i) a more compact design enabling longer dissolution times and, (ii) the continuous supply of fresh solvent which effectively reduces solubility limitations. At equal solid throughput and solvent consumed, the packed bed reactor extracted 27%–55% more calcium than the stirred batch reactor for AN concentrations of 0.25–2.0 mol/kg.

After dissolution, about 300 L of liquid is retained in the reactor per ton of material. The trapped aqueous ammonium nitrate solution was displaced by flushing the reactor with an equal amount of fresh water, thereby recovering a solution containing 80% of the AN. The solvent recovery stage is crucial; without it, the emissions related to AN synthesis to make up for the losses are comparable to, if not larger than, the amount of CO₂ stored by the process.

The study demonstrated the good performance of a packed bed reactor for the leaching of calcium from RCA for indirect mineral carbonation. To determine the optimal operating conditions, the developed model should be integrated with environmental and economic assessments. Furthermore, conducting larger-scale studies will be necessary to evaluate the automated operation of a packed bed reactor, the time required for loading and emptying the reactor's contents, and the pressure build-up in the reactor.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Antonio Gasós: Conceptualization, Data curation, Methodology, Software, Visualization, Writing – original draft. **Mattheus Meijssen:** Conceptualization, Writing – review & editing. **Marco Mazzotti:** Conceptualization, Supervision, Writing – review & editing.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare the following financial interests/personal relationships which may be considered as potential competing interests: Marco Mazzotti reports financial support was provided by European Union. Marco Mazzotti reports a relationship with Neustark AG that includes: consulting or advisory.

Data availability

Data will be made available on request.

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Appendix A. Supplementary data

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